

Empowerment of Women in Chetan Bhagat's Novel Revolution 2020 and Two States: The Story of My Marriage

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Abstract

Chetan Bhagat is a contemporary writer who exposes the empowerment of women and creates a new image for modern women through his novels. He lightens the power of women in every field such as education, politics and decision making etc. In the novel Two States Ananya Swaminathan, a Tamilian girl falls in love with a Punjabi boy Krish Malhotra, the protagonist of the novel. She moves to Delhi and persuades Krish's family and get acceptance for their marriage proposal. Chetan Bhagat expresses that women are given respect and they gets succeed in their life. Aarti, the female protagonist of the novel Revolution 2020 had a pre-marital sex with Gopal and later married Raghav. It proves the world that both the men and women are treated equally. The women are given freedom to choose their life individually. Chetan Bhagat implies that the time has changed from treating men as superior and women as inferior to both the sex are equal. It shows that women deserve a respectful place in the society. Thus, the paper represents the identity of women in Chetan Bhagat's novel.

Keywords: Empowerment, Identity, Freedom, Equality, Respect.

Full Paper

Women empowerment refers to the complete emancipation of women from socio-economic shackles of dependency and deprivation. Empowerment of women would mean encouraging women to be self-radiant, economically independent, have positive self-esteem, generate confidence to face any difficult situation and achieve participation in socio-political development endeavours. The person who tries to empower women is called Feminist and the process is names as Feminism. It has gained more importance in the 21st century. Feminism is not only giving equal rights to vote and assets but also to choose their own life. Chetan Bhagat explained this concept through the novel Two States. Similarly in the novel Revolution 2020, Aarti

the female protagonist of the novel is portrayed as a tuned girl towards her ambition. She starts her job as an air hostess in Indian Airlines. She has turned into a working woman and started to earn. It shows the modernized women surviving in the 21st century. Besides working as a air hostess she gets engaged in “Aviation Academy” to fight for the freedom of women as a feminist. Through the character Aarti, Chetan Bhagat tries to explore that parent also acceptable to send their daughters to various job fields.

At first Aarti worked as an air hostess and later she joined as “Guest Relations Trainee.” In earlier days women hesitates to work as a guest relations trainee but now the scenario is changed. Aarti has a love affair with Raghav and Gopal, who were her childhood friends. Initially she have crush towards Raghav but he doesn't have enough time to spend for Aarti. So, Aarti turns her love towards Gopal without any hesitation. Gopal and Aarti started to visit cafes, hotels, movies and parks twice or thrice in a week at Varanasi. Through these incidents Chetan Bhagat explains that women are treated equally and their status has become equal to men. The novel also enacts the theme that women are getting empowered equal to men. She also had drinks with her friends in social places.

Empowerment of women is not only getting equal status to vote, assets or gender. A woman gets empowered when she chooses his own life without anyone's influence. Aarti being a modern girl wants to have luxurious life. She is very gel to adopt for a modern style. While Aarti is working as a receptionist, she had a sexual relationship with Gopal. At the time she asked to check Gopal if other co-workers of Aarti are watching her visit to the room. It exposes the practical thinking of Aarti. Chetan Bhagat shows women characters as intelligent, smart and confident. The novel Revolution 2020 also represents that women also started to use technologies such as messages and e-mail to converse one another. Chetan Bhagat also implies that modern women also feels excited to have relationships with two persons and to have pre-marital sex. It shows that women started to cross the restrictions given by the family and society. They have started to live their life for happiness and enjoyment.

Later, Aarti also started to involve in politics with the help of Gopal and the MLA Shuklaji. She started to meet politicians along with Gopal and took a part in the life of MLA. She also visits so many villages along with other politicians. It makes the reader to get aware of women involving in politics. Thus, the novel Revolution 2020 proves that women have started to engage in every field and strong enough to lead their own life. Aarti is a good looking women and her description is given in the beginning of the novel Revolution 2020. It is expressed in the following lines
I sat up straight and craned my neck to see Aarti Pratap Pradhman, roll number one. She wore a white skirt, white shirt, red cardigan and had ribbons in her plaits, and she faced the teacher more seriously as she sat down.

‘Eww’, Aarti screamed and jumped up. She picked up a chocolate-stained ruler from her seat. The back of her skirt had chocolate stains. ‘Oh my God!’ Aarti’s shrill voice made the entire class take notice.(11: Rev 20)

In the novel Two States, the female protagonist Ananya Swaminathan who is a Tamilian girl is depicted as a woman of empowerment in the 21st Century. She belongs to a Brahmin family, a middle class background. She is a suitable girl to fit for their customs and traditions. She gets educated to bring her parents dream in to reality. She has sincerely involved in relationship with a Punjabi boy Krish Malhotra who is from New Delhi. The love affair of Ananya towards the north Indian boy irritates her parents. Ananya as a 21st Century women don't want to elope and get married with Krish. She needs to marry Krish with her parents' consent. Ananya moved to Delhi to convince Krish parents. There she attended Krish's cousin marriage. Unfortunately the marriage was to break because of the inability of Krish family to pay the dowry. Now, Ananya interfered and

make the situation calm by her intellectual speech. The way she convinced attracts Krish's parents and the allowed Krish to marry Ananya. Ananya's persuading speech in the marriage is given below

'Sit down,' Ananya said. Duke compiled instantly. Ananya turned to everyone. 'Listen, all brothers and sisters of Duke, there isn't going to be any Accent. The elders have shown their true colours, now it is down to Duke and all of you. If he wants to take Minti with respect, he should say so. If he doesn't then he is just a schmuck and we don't wasn't the wedding.

'Ananya beta. . . .' Raji mama came to us as the youngsters' meeting had gone for too long.

'Almost done, uncle,' Ananya said. 'Five minutes, Duke. Make up your mind.'

Everyone fell silent as Ananya Swaminathan, brand manager HLL, MBA, rated best girl by popular vote at IIMA and rated best girlfriend by my own vote, forced the younger generation in Duke's family to think.

(214: Two States)

Ananya Swaminathan is a girl of clear thinking. She asks Krish to come her room for study. Once they talk about their future Krish says that he want to become a writer. He expected that Ananya will laugh at his desire. But to the change Ananya accepted his dream whole heartedly and encourages Krish. He feels that he is lucky to have her girl Ananya who gives respect to his dreams and guides him in a good way. Ananya being a 21st Century modern woman is deeply rooted with Indian culture. She has achieved in her life. She feels proud to be a woman and still ties to her family bonding. Both the families did not accept for their marriage at first. Later, Ananya convinced Krish's family and Krish convinced Ananya's family. At the end of the novel, Krish and Ananya get married with their parents' consent. It proves that women of 21st Century are intelligent and confident. Thus, Chetan Bhagat represents the power of women through his novels.

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